

Infrastructural facilities and Electricity Assessment in the Implementation of Public Private Partnership Policy Among Fish Farmers in Edo State.

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Abstract

The study examined Infrastructural facilities and Electricity assessment in the implementation of Public Private Partnership Policy among fish farmers in Edo state. The study adopted the Ex-post Facto Research Design, using the descriptive survey method. The population of the study comprised 1,532 fish farmers in Edo state. The sample size of the study was 390 fish farmers drawn through a Stratified Proportionate Sampling Technique. The instrument that was used to collect data in this study is a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was validated by experts in Vocational Education Department and Measurement and Evaluation, Delta State University, Abraka, including the research supervisors. Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient was used to estimate the reliability index. The research questions were answered with the aid of Means and Standard Deviations. The hypotheses were tested using independent samples t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study indicated that the level of enjoyment of the provision of infrastructural facilities and electricity by fish farmers in Edo state is very low. The study also found that there is no significant difference between urban and rural fish farmers in Edo state in enjoying Public Private Partnership in the provision of infrastructural facilities and that there is significant difference between male and female fish farmers in Edo state in enjoying Public Private Partnership in the provision of infrastructural facilities and electricity. The study however, showed that there is a significant difference between urban and rural fish farmers in Edo state in enjoying Public Private Partnership in the provision of electricity. On the basis of these findings, the study recommended amongst others, that government should implement targeted awareness campaigns to educate fish farmers about the benefits and opportunities associated with PPP initiatives.

Keywords:

Infrastructural facilities; Electricity Assessment; Public Private Partnership Polic; Fish Farmers; Edo State

Introduction

The United Nations (UN) in 2015 came up with the 2030 agenda for Sustainable Development, also termed Agenda 2030. The agenda was a universal plan for global cooperation on sustainable development for the period of 2015 to 2030. The meeting of UN nations for the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) was necessitated by the need for global collaboration and concerted action to address the complex and interrelated challenges facing the world. The meeting aimed to foster international partnerships, develop implementation strategies, and ensure accountability in the pursuit of sustainable development by 2030. The meeting mandated the creation of an Open Working Group to come up with a draft agenda that gave rise to the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. That is, setting target that must be achieved between 2015 and 2030.

The agenda comprised of 17 goals, and these are (1) no poverty (2) Zero Hunger (3) Good Health and Well-being (4) Quality Education (5) Gender Equality (6) Clean Water and Sanitation (7) Affordable and Clean Energy (8) Decent Work and Economic Growth (9) Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure (10) Reduced Inequality (11) Sustainable Cities and Communities (12) Responsible Consumption and Production (13) Climate Action (14) Life Below Water (15) Life on Land (16) Peace and Justice Strong Institutions and (17) Partnerships to achieve the Goal. The goal that is of interest to the researcher is the goal 2 of zero hunger.

Unfortunately, extreme hunger and malnutrition remain a huge barrier to development in many countries. There are 821 million people estimated to be chronically undernourished as at 2017, often as a direct consequence of environmental degradation, drought and biodiversity loss (United Nations Development Programme, UNDP, 2022). Over 90 million children under five are dangerously underweight (UNDP, 2022). Undernourishment and severe food insecurity appear to be increasing in almost all regions of Africa, including Nigeria.

The Sustainable Development Goal 2 on zero hunger aims to end all forms of hunger and malnutrition by 2030, making sure all people—especially children—have sufficient and nutritious food all year round. This involves promoting sustainable agricultural production, supporting small-scale farmers and increased access to land, technology and markets. It also requires international cooperation to ensure investment in infrastructure and technology to improve agricultural productivity. Agricultural enterprises that can aid in achieving the goal of zero hunger by increasing food production, improving food security, and promoting sustainable

farming practices include crop farming, livestock farming, agroforestry, organic farming, urban agriculture, sustainable irrigation and water management, agricultural research and innovation, farmer training and capacity building, market access and value chain development and fish farming.

Fish farming remains one of the key sectors for driving the economy forward. According to Oscar (2020), Nigeria is the largest aquaculture fish producer in Sub-Saharan Africa and close to 19 million people, directly and indirectly, are employed in the fishery industry. In the last three decades, aquaculture production has grown 12 per cent per year in Nigeria as compared to the world average of 8% (National Bureau of Statistics, NBS, 2022). Common fish species grown by farmers include Carp, tilapia and catfish species.

Fish farming as a budding industry has the potential to flourish and meet up with the large deficit between fish production and consumption in Nigeria, if properly exploited. The Federal Department of Fisheries (FDF, 2022), disclosed that the Nigerian coastline has huge potential for inland and offshore fish farming. It also stated that besides increasing the availability of fish food, especially in the coastal areas, it offers commercial prospects for sustainable fish farming business in Nigeria.

According to a 2018–2022 report from WorldFish Nigeria Strategy, Nigeria produced over 1 million metric tons of fish but left a deficit of 800,000 metric tons, which is imported from other countries every year (Oscar, 2020). Also, the WorldFish study on Nigerian Aquaculture shows that if the factors such as price and customers' demand remain unchanged, it will result in the demand-supply gap of 450,000-metric tons in the near future. Fish production needs to be doubled by 2030 and losses after harvest should be reduced in order to meet this growing demand.

The economic recession and insufficient income have raised concerns about a significant decline in per capita fish consumption in Nigeria, which could have negative implications for the country's nutritional status. Furthermore, the existing aquaculture practices are contributing to environmental pollution and fish mortality. The high cost of imported fish feeds used by farmers is resulting in minimal profits, discouraging many from continuing their involvement in the fishing industry.

Nigeria has not been spared from natural hazards that have included flooding, drought and the global financial crisis. These have resulted in the destruction of numerous fisheries and severe impacts on the development of the sector. Of the over 210 species of fishes in Nigerian water bodies, little fraction of them is receiving cultivation attention from fish farmers. While the popular fish species such as the catfish and tilapia keep blossoming in the markets, the reverse is the case with many other species whose abandonment has led to a gradual extinction.

The term “Public–Private Partnership” describes a range of possible relationships among public and private entities in the context of infrastructure and other services (Gwary, et al., 2016). It describes a government service or private business venture which is funded and operated through a partnership of government and one or more private sector companies (Johnson, 2010). It is essentially a partnership between public sector organizations and private sector investors and business for the purpose of designing, planning, financing, constructing, providing and/or operating infrastructure, facilities or related services to rural and urban dwellers.

The Public Private Partnership (PPP) procurement method has been used across the country in the generation of power, management of waste disposal, highway and street cleaning and maintenance, among others. This method can also be employed in the implementation of fish farming. In view of the foregoing, the aim of this study is to assess the implementation of Public Private Partnership (PPP) among fish farmers in the area of fingerlings and feeds.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to assess the extent infrastructural facilities and electricity are enjoyed in the Public Private Partnership Policy among fish farmers in Edo State. The specific objectives of the study were to:

1. ascertain the extent to which fish farmers in Edo State enjoy Public Private partnership in the provision of infrastructural facilities;
2. determine the extent to which fish farmers in Edo State enjoy Public Private partnership in the provision of electricity;

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study as to:

1. what extent do fish farmers in Edo State enjoy Public Private partnership in the provision of infrastructural facilities?
2. what extent do fish farmers in Edo State enjoy Public Private partnership in the provision of electricity?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between urban and rural fish farmers in Edo State in enjoying Public Private partnership in the provision of infrastructural facilities
2. There is no significant difference between urban and rural fish farmers in Edo State in enjoying Public Private partnership in the provision of electricity
3. There is no significant difference between male and female fish farmers in Edo State in enjoying Public Private partnership in the provision of infrastructural facilities
4. There is no significant difference between male and female fish farmers in Edo State in enjoying Public Private partnership in the provision of electricity

Research Methods

The study adopted the *Ex-Post Facto* Research Design, using the descriptive survey method. The descriptive research design is a type of research design that aims at systematically obtaining an existing information to describe a phenomenon, situation, or population that has already occurred (Dehalwar & Sharma, 2023). The reason for this design is because the researcher had no interest in manipulating the independent variable. This design was used to examine the extent to which fish farmers enjoy Public Private partnership in the provision of infrastructural facilities and electricity.

The population of the study comprised 1,532 fish farmers in Edo State, Nigeria. The distribution of fish farmers is shown in Table 1.

Table 1:

Distribution of Fish farmers by Local Government Areas in Edo State

S/N	Local Government Area	Number of Fish Farmers
1	Akoko-Edo	40
2	Egor	25
3	Esan South East	25
4	Esan West	20
5	Essa North East	20
6	Essan Central	51
7	Etsako Central	32
8	Etsako East	121
9	Etsako West	200
10	Igueben	23
11	Ikpoba Okha	577
12	Oredo	126
13	Orhionmwon	15
14	Ovia North-East	54
15	Ovia South West	18
16	Owan East	50
17	Owan West	50
18	Uhunmwode	85
Total		1,532

Source: Department of Fisheries, Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security, Edo State (2023)

The sample size for the study was 390 fish farmers in Edo State, which represents 25% of the entire population. The sample was drawn from the 18 Local Government Areas of the State through a Stratified Proportionate Sampling Technique. This sampling technique is a probability sampling technique in which different strata in a population are identified and in which the number of elements drawn from each stratum is proportionate to the relative number of elements in each stratum.

5. The reason of this choice of the proportionate stratified sampling technique is because all the Local Government Areas in Edo State do not have equal number of fish farmers. Hence, there was the need to represent the population of fish farmers in each Local Government Area

Table 2:

Sample distribution of Fish farmers by Local Government Area in Edo State

S/N	Local Government Area	Number of Fish Farmers	
		Population Size	Sample Size (25%)
1	Akoko-Edo	40	10
2	Egor	25	6
3	Esan South East	25	6
4	Esan West	20	5
5	Essa North East	20	5
6	Essan Central	51	13
7	Etsako Central	32	8
8	Etsako East	121	31
9	Etsako West	200	51
10	Igueben	23	6
11	Ikpoba Okha	577	146
12	Oredo	126	32
13	Orhionmwon	15	4
14	Ovia North-East	54	14
15	Ovia South West	18	5
16	Owan East	50	13
17	Owan West	50	13
18	Uhunmwode	85	22
	Total	1,532	390

Instrument

The instrument that was used to collect data in this study is a structured questionnaire. The Questionnaire titled Questionnaire on Implementation of Public Private Partnership among Fish Farmers (QIPPPFF). The questionnaire contains three sections. Section A consisted of information on the personal data of the respondents, section B contains information on Provision of infrastructural facilities (13 items), section C contains information on Provision of electricity (5 items). Items in sections B and C of the questionnaire are structured on a four-point scale of very low extent, low extent, high extent and very high extent representing 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively.

The questionnaire was validated by experts in Vocational Education Department and Measurement and Evaluation, Delta State University, Abraka, including the research supervisors. In order to ensure the face and content validity of the instrument, copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the experts, who went through and made suggestions for

correction. The corrections were effected by the researcher to get the final draft. Based on the judgement of the experts, the instrument was considered valid.

The questionnaire was administered to 50 fish farmers in Delta State in order to establish the reliability of the instrument. The data obtained were analysed using Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient. The following coefficients were obtained: Provision of Infrastructural facilities = 0.96; Provision of Electricity = 0.80. The questionnaire was administered directly to the respondents by the researcher. Five research assistants were recruited and trained to provide support. The researcher went to the various fish farms to meet the fish farmers in their various Local Government Areas. Salient areas in the questionnaire were explained to the respondents by the researcher for proper understanding. The instrument was retrieved immediately.

The data were analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The research questions were answered with the aid of Means and Standard Deviations. Based on the 4-point scale, the items with mean scores from 2.50-4.00 shows high extent, while items with mean scores below 2.50 shows low extent. The hypotheses were tested using independent samples t-test at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent do fish farmers in Edo State enjoy Public Private partnership in terms of provision of infrastructural facilities?

Table 3:

Mean analysis of the extent to which fish farmers in Edo State enjoy Public Private partnership in terms of provision of infrastructural facilities

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Generators	2.11	0.95	Low
2	Measuring Tape	2.05	1.03	Low
3	Pegs	2.03	0.97	Low
4	Vat	2.02	0.88	Low
5	Strings	1.92	0.93	Low
6	Land Facility	1.89	1.07	Low
7	Buckets and Tubs	1.88	0.94	Low
8	Thermometer	1.85	0.92	Low
9	Water Pumps	1.85	0.84	Low
10	Weighing scale	1.85	0.96	Low
11	Pollution-free Water	1.84	0.87	Low
12	Aerators/Air Pump	1.79	0.90	Low
13	Harvesting materials	1.78	0.82	Low
Average Mean		1.91	0.93	Low

Criterion Mean = 2.50

Table 3 shows the mean analysis of the extent to which fish farmers in Edo State enjoy Public Private partnership in terms of provision of infrastructural facilities. The result shows that the mean score ranged from 1.78 to 2.11, with an average mean of 1.91. The criterion mean is 2.50, which is less than the criterion mean of 2.50. This means that fish farmers in Edo State do not enjoy Public Private partnership in terms of provision of infrastructural facilities.

Research Question 2: To what extent do fish farmers in Edo State enjoy Public Private partnership in terms of provision of electricity?

Table 4:

Mean analysis of the extent to which fish farmers in Edo State enjoy Public Private partnership in terms of provision of electricity

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Provision of generators	1.89	0.89	Low
2	Provision of PMS	1.85	1.05	Low
3	Provision of diesel	1.68	0.95	Low
4	Provision of electricity	1.65	1.00	Low
5	Provision of solar system	1.64	0.90	Low
Average Mean		1.74	0.96	Low

Criterion Mean = 2.50

Table 4 shows the mean analysis of the extent to which fish farmers in Edo State enjoy Public Private partnership in terms of provision of electricity. The result shows that the mean score ranged from 1.64 to 1.89, with an average mean of 1.74. The criterion mean is 2.50, which is less than the criterion mean of 2.50. This means that fish farmers in Edo State do not enjoy Public Private partnership in terms of provision of electricity.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between urban and rural fish farmers in Edo State in regard to enjoying Public Private partnership in terms of provision of infrastructural facilities

Table 5:

t-test analysis of the difference between urban and rural fish farmers in Edo State in regard to enjoying Public Private partnership in terms of provision of infrastructural facilities

Location	N	Mean	SD	df	t	P	Remark
Urban	209	1.91	0.62				
Rural	172	1.91	0.61	379	0.09	0.93	Not Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 5 shows the t-test analysis of the difference between urban and rural fish farmers in Edo State in regard to enjoying Public Private partnership in terms of provision of infrastructural facilities. The result shows that urban ($M = 1.91, SD = 0.62$) rural ($M = 1.91, SD$

= 0.61); $t(379) = 0.09, p > 0.05$ level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted, meaning that there is no significant difference between urban and rural fish farmers in Edo State in regard to enjoying Public Private partnership in terms of provision of infrastructural facilities.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between urban and rural fish farmers in Edo State in regard to enjoying Public Private partnership in terms of provision of electricity

Table 6:

t-test analysis of the difference between urban and rural fish farmers in Edo State in regard to enjoying Public Private partnership in terms of provision of electricity

Location	<i>n</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>P</i>	Remark
Urban	209	1.89	0.75				
Rural	172	1.55	0.66	379	4.58	0.000	Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 6 shows the t-test analysis of the difference between urban and rural fish farmers in Edo State in regard to enjoying Public Private partnership in terms of provision of electricity. The result shows that urban ($M = 1.89, SD = 0.75$) rural ($M = 1.55, SD = 0.66$); $t(379) = 4.58, p < 0.05$ level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, meaning that there is a significant difference between urban and rural fish farmers in Edo State in regard to enjoying Public Private partnership in terms of provision of electricity. Urban fish farmers in Edo State seems to enjoy Public Private Partnership in terms of provision of electricity more than their rural counterparts.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between male and female fish farmers in Edo State in regard to enjoying Public Private partnership in terms of provision of infrastructural facilities

Table 7:

t-test analysis of the difference between male and female fish farmers in Edo State in regard to enjoying Public Private partnership in terms of provision of infrastructural facilities

Gender	<i>n</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>P</i>	Remark
Male	245	1.89	0.60				
Female	140	1.93	0.65	379	0.60	0.55	Not Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 7 shows the t-test analysis of the difference between male and female fish farmers in Edo State in regard to enjoying Public Private partnership in terms of provision of infrastructural facilities. The result shows that male ($M = 1.89, SD = 0.60$) female ($M = 1.93, SD = 0.65$); $t(379) = 0.60, p > 0.05$ level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted,

meaning that there is no significant difference between male and female fish farmers in Edo State in regard to enjoying Public Private partnership in terms of provision of infrastructural facilities.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference between male and female fish farmers in Edo State in regard to enjoying Public Private partnership in terms of provision of electricity

Table 8:

t-test analysis of the difference between male and female fish farmers in Edo State in regard to enjoying Public Private partnership in terms of provision of electricity

Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t	P	Remark
Male	245	1.63	0.64				
Female	140	1.93	0.81	379	3.98	0.000	Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 8 shows the t-test analysis of the difference between male and female fish farmers in Edo State in regard to enjoying Public Private partnership in terms of provision of electricity. The result shows that male ($M = 1.63, SD = 0.64$) female ($M = 1.93, SD = 0.81$); $t(379) = 3.98, p < 0.05$ level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, meaning that there is a significant difference between male and female fish farmers in Edo State in regard to enjoying Public Private partnership in terms of provision of electricity. Female fish farmers in Edo State seems to enjoy Public Private Partnership in terms of provision of electricity more than their male counterparts.

Discussion of Results

Extent to which Fish Farmers in Edo State Enjoy Public Private Partnership in Terms of Provision of Infrastructural Facilities

The third finding revealed that fish farmers in Edo State do not enjoy Public Private partnership in terms of provision of infrastructural facilities. This finding raises notable concerns for the development and sustainability of the aquaculture sector in the region. Infrastructural support is crucial for efficient and productive fish farming operations, encompassing facilities such as ponds, storage units, and processing centers. The absence of PPP involvement in this aspect may pose challenges to the overall growth and viability of fish farming enterprises in the state.

A corresponding hypothesis showed that there is no significant difference between urban and rural fish farmers in Edo State in regard to enjoying Public Private partnership in terms of provision of infrastructural facilities. This implies a uniform challenge across both

urban and rural areas, emphasizing the need for a comprehensive and inclusive approach to address the lack of PPP support for infrastructure in the fish farming sector. It suggests that the lack of PPP support is not specific to certain groups but rather a broader challenge faced by the entire fish farming community in Edo State.

It was also found that there is no significant difference between male and female fish farmers in Edo State in regard to enjoying Public Private partnership in terms of provision of infrastructural facilities. This finding may indicate a more equitable distribution of support, at least in terms of facilities. Possible reasons for this finding could include limited awareness and engagement with PPP opportunities, bureaucratic hurdles in accessing support, or a general lack of targeted initiatives for infrastructural development in the aquaculture sector.

The above finding agrees with the result of previous studies. For instance, Onuigbo et al. (2019) found that existing PPPs in Nigerian aquaculture primarily target fingerling provision and technology transfer, neglecting infrastructure development. Edo State might have followed this national trend, leading to a lack of PPP engagement in infrastructure projects specific to fish farming. National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2020) stated that rural areas in Edo State often face significant infrastructure deficits, including access to roads, electricity, and water. This might deter private partners from engaging in PPPs due to increased project costs and logistical complexities. World Bank (2022) however, emphasised that new PPP models focusing on rural infrastructure development are emerging in Nigeria.

Extent to which Fish Farmers in Edo State Enjoy Public Private Partnership in Terms of Provision of Electricity

The fourth finding showed that fish farmers in Edo State do not enjoy Public Private partnership in terms of provision of electricity. This finding highlights a crucial challenge that could impact the efficiency and productivity of aquaculture operations in the region. Access to reliable electricity is essential for various aspects of fish farming, including water oxygenation, temperature control, and the operation of equipment. The absence of PPP support in this area suggests a potential hindrance to the overall development and sustainability of the fish farming sector in Edo State.

A corresponding hypothesis revealed that there is a significant difference between urban and rural fish farmers in Edo State in regard to enjoying Public Private partnership in terms of provision of electricity. Urban fish farmers in Edo State seems to enjoy Public Private

Partnership in terms of provision of electricity more than their rural counterparts. This urban-rural disparity could be attributed to infrastructure development patterns, with urban areas potentially having better-established electricity networks or being more attractive to private investments.

It was also found that there is a significant difference between male and female fish farmers in Edo State in regard to enjoying Public Private partnership in terms of provision of electricity. Female fish farmers in Edo State seems to enjoy Public Private Partnership in terms of provision of electricity more than their male counterparts. This finding raises questions about the factors contributing to this disparity. It may indicate targeted efforts or support structures that are more accessible to female fish farmers or unique challenges faced by male fish farmers in accessing PPP for electricity provision.

The above finding agrees with the result of previous studies. For instance, the Nigerian Electricity Supply Industry (NESI, 2023) stated that existing PPPs in the Nigerian energy sector primarily target grid-based electricity expansion, neglecting off-grid solutions suitable for rural areas. This might limit PPP engagement in providing electricity access to rural fish farmers in Edo State. The World Bank (2022) also stated that innovative PPP models specifically targeting off-grid energy access are emerging in Nigeria. However, International Energy Agency (IEA, 2023) found that mini-grid projects, often supported by PPPs, are becoming increasingly popular for rural electrification in Africa.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that fish farmers in Edo State encounter limitations in PPP involvement across critical areas in the provision of infrastructural facilities and electricity. The disparities observed between urban and rural fish farmers highlight the uneven distribution of PPP benefits, with urban farmers seemingly enjoying more support, particularly in terms of electricity. This urban-rural divide suggests a need for targeted efforts to address the specific challenges faced by rural fish farmers, ensuring that they have equitable access to essential resources and services.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings and conclusion drawn, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should implement targeted awareness campaigns to educate fish farmers about the benefits and opportunities associated with PPP initiatives.

2. Government should conduct outreach programs in both urban and rural areas to ensure that all fish farmers are informed about available PPP support
3. Government should work with private entities to develop and maintain infrastructure that supports fish farming in both urban and rural areas.

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